

CYCLIC STRESS-STRAIN AND FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF METAL

MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Large variations in the fatigue behaviour of metal matrix composites have been recorded. Under conditions which satisfy the Coffin-Manson relationship for high strain fatigue attempts have been made to forecast the life of such composites, without too much success. The weakness of the approach comes from the assumptions that have to be made about matrix behaviour during cyclic plastic straining. Hence, an assessment of matrix behaviour under cyclic loading has been carried out on continuous tungsten wire reinforced copper composites at a series of volume fractions (0.1 - 0.6) and fibre diameters (10 - 50 μm). The load-unload behaviour at stresses sufficient to cause matrix plastic deformation is not typical of conventional materials, i.e. it reverts from an open loop back to a linear 'elastic' response. Composite friction stress values have been found for each composite tested and these show considerable deviation from 'rule of mixture' values. Both of these results have been interpreted in terms of the existence and rearrangement of dislocation substructures, the effective density of which change with increasing volume fraction and decreasing fibre spacing. At increasing strain levels (0.1 and 0.4%) the matrix cyclic stress becomes independent of interfibre spacing, provided the fibre volume fraction exceeds 0.2. This kind of behaviour indicates that similar fatigue lives would be expected in all these composites if they are all subjected to high strain fatigue.

1.0 Introduction

Attempts have been made by a number of workers⁽¹⁻³⁾ to explain the cyclic stress-strain behaviour of metal matrix composites particularly at the stage where the fibres are elastic and the matrix is plastic. In composites unidirectionally reinforced with continuous fibres, it has been demonstrated that after a certain level of prestressing a stable closed hysteresis loop results that remains reproducible for several hundred cycles. Such materials possess the advantageous property of a high damping capacity. Analyses of these loops in terms of the stress-strain data for individual fibres and the separate matrix usually are imprecise because certain assumptions have to be made about the cyclic strain hardening characteristics of the matrix. For example Kelly and Bomford⁽²⁾ have used the general relationship

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_m + c \varepsilon_p^n \quad \dots (1)$$

where σ_y is the cyclic yield stress, ε_p is the plastic strain, $\sigma_m = \sigma_y$ at $\varepsilon_p = 0$ and c and n are constants. Two different types of matrix behaviour were investigated:

- (a) the matrix behaved in a linear fashion where $n = 1$, and
- (b) with parabolic hardening where $n = \frac{1}{2}$.

Data from these assumptions have been inserted into an equation which purports to represent the composite cyclic behaviour^(1,2):

$$\Delta \varepsilon_p = \frac{2\sigma_c - 2\sigma_y [(E_f/E_m) V_f + (1 - V_f)]}{E_f V_f + U(1 - V_f)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where σ_c is the composite stress, E_f and E_m are the elastic moduli of the fibre and matrix respectively, V_f is the fibre volume fraction and U is the effective modulus of the yielded matrix.

Several authors⁽⁴⁻⁶⁾ have shown using monotonic tensile tests that in certain composites the metal matrix has a much higher work hardening capacity than that predicted for a metal without fibres. This situation is particularly noticeable as fibre diameter decreases at high fibre volume fractions. In such composites the values of the yield stress σ_y and the modulus of the yielded matrix, U , should increase as fibre spacing decreases thus reducing the plastic strain range as given by equation (2).

Measurements^(7,8) made by the present authors on a series of composites prepared from tungsten wires of small diameter (10 - 50 μm) and a polycrystalline copper matrix have shown that strengthening (during monotonic testing) was enhanced by the grain size and the abnormally high dislocation density of the copper.

It was maintained that such dislocation densities became a major strengthening factor if:

- (i) a significant difference in thermal expansion coefficient existed between fibre and matrix,
- (ii) a thermal cycle is involved in composite fabrication,
- (iii) the interfibre spacing is in the neighbourhood of 50 μm (obviously this distance does depend on (i) and (ii)).

Using this information in conjunction with the microscope observations of Hancock and Grosskreutz⁽⁹⁾ and Chawla and Metzger⁽¹⁰⁾ on samples taken from composites containing large diameter fibres it was suggested that high dislocation densities exist at the fibre-matrix interface and then decay rapidly to a level found in the bulk matrix, i.e. at a distance of $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$ from the interface. Further it was maintained that the matrix strengthening begins to be observed when these distributions overlap and that the degree of overlapping determines the extent of the strengthening.

The existence of such dislocation distributions should clearly affect the cyclic hardening behaviour of metal matrices. However, it is difficult to forecast such behaviour from monotonic tests for it is well known⁽¹¹⁾ that during cyclic loading of unreinforced copper that dislocation substructure size of $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ are set up, these being much smaller than those expected in monotonic testing. The series of experiments described here set out to measure the cyclic stress-strain behaviour of a polycrystalline copper matrix as the tungsten wire diameter and volume fraction are varied. These measurements should indicate whether cyclic hardening occurs above the enhanced level found in monotonic tests and also provide further information on the dislocation distribution between fibres. Such information should give an insight into the fatigue behaviour of these composites which to date have proved difficult to forecast purely from cyclic stress-strain behaviour.

2.0 Experimental Procedure

2.1 Materials

Copper was unidirectionally reinforced with commercial tungsten wire with diameters in the range 10 to 50 μm . The resultant composites had fibre volume fractions lying in the range 0.1 to 0.6. The mechanical properties of the tungsten wires are given in a previous paper⁽⁸⁾ together with the details of how they were measured.

The copper matrix was produced by electrodeposition from an

acid sulphate bath, containing 188 g/litre of cupric sulphate and 74 g/litre of sulphuric acid at a current density of 200 A/m².

2.2 Specimen preparation

The composites were fabricated by the filament winding-electrodeposition-vacuum hot pressing route. Specimens for cyclic stress-strain testing measuring approximately 100 mm x 5 mm x 0.7 mm, were cut from the hot pressed blanks. Small blocks of copper were bonded to each end of these pieces to provide a gripping area for the tests. The fibre volume fraction of the composites was measured accurately by weighing a piece of each specimen, removing the matrix with acid and then weighing the remaining fibres.

Unreinforced copper specimens were prepared by hot pressing thin electrodeposited sheets whose thickness was the same as the monolayer sheets used for preparing the composites.

2.3 Cyclic stress-strain testing

The tests were carried out in a servo-hydraulic machine under load control conditions. Strain in the specimens was measured with metal foil strain gauges bonded to the surface with Eastmann 910 adhesive. The strain sensitivity was 10⁻⁶.

Load-unload tests were performed on specimens at each combination of fibre diameter and volume fraction. Starting with the material in the as-pressed condition specimens were loaded and unloaded at stress intervals of 5 MN/m² below 30 MN/m², 10 MN/m² between 30 MN/m² and 100 MN/m² and in 50 MN/m² intervals thereafter to failure. At each stress level the specimen was cycled until a closed loop was formed (i.e. with no residual strain on unloading). This process of loading and unloading and loop stabilisation was continued to failure.

A series of load-unload tests of this type gave results from which it was possible to obtain information concerning the cyclic stress-strain behaviour of the materials including friction stress, cyclic hardening and specific damping capacity.

3.0 Results

Table I lists the composites that were tested in terms of wire diameter, fibre volume fraction and interfibre spacing, the latter was calculated assuming hexagonal packing of the fibres⁽⁸⁾. The object was to work at three nominal interfibre spacing values of 12, 18 and 24 μm and to vary the volume fraction accordingly.

3.1 Low stress load-unload composite behaviour

It was found that for all the composites tested the loading and unloading lines coincided if the maximum stress did not exceed approximately 10 MN/m^2 . This represented the elastic region for the composite and allowed the elastic modulus values to be calculated, the values having been given in an earlier paper⁽⁸⁾. On increasing the stress above the elastic region all the composites followed the pattern shown in the schematic diagram of Figure 1. After the initial all elastic behaviour given by loop 1 the material would eventually yield giving rise to a loop of the shape shown by loop 2 in which the unloading line was linear and therefore elastic at least to a strain sensitivity of 10^{-6} . The next load-unload cycle to the same stress remained all-elastic as shown by loop 3. Such behaviour may be repeated at higher stresses as shown by loops 4 and 5 until at a stress level approximately twice that at which initial yielding was observed a non-linear unloading line was obtained (loop 6) and the next load-unload cycle to the same stress gave rise to a closed hysteresis loop (loop 7). As the stress was increased non-linear loading and unloading was always observed and several load-unload cycles were needed to form a closed loop, the number ranging from two at low stresses to around ten cycles when approaching the failure stress.

The behaviour as depicted by loops 2 and 3, where apparently elastic unloading occurs after previous yielding did not occur for the unreinforced specimen of copper prepared by the same fabrication route as the composite samples.

3.2 Cyclic stress-strain curve for the composites

When the maximum cyclic stress and strain values for the stable hysteresis loops are plotted the result is the cyclic stress-strain curve for that specimen. Such a curve does not represent the stress-strain behaviour of the material when cycling to a given stress, but the stabilised state of the material in response to increasing cyclic stresses. However, in practice it is found that the loading line of the hysteresis loop closely resembles the cyclic stress-strain curve.

Cyclic stress-strain curves were obtained for all the composites listed in Table I and these are shown in Figure 2. The curves do not extend to the point of failure but to the strain level which could be measured practically. It should be remembered that the stresses and strains are for the stable cyclic state of the material and in achieving this stability considerably larger strains will have been endured by the specimens during the cyclic hardening process, particularly at low fibre volume fractions. It can be seen from Figure 2 that for a given cyclic strain the corresponding cyclic stress increases with volume

fraction.

Cyclic stress-strain tests that were carried out on a number of fibres extracted from as-pressed composites showed that whilst there was detectable cyclic plastic strain in the tungsten the amount was insignificant when compared with that existing in the composites. Hence, it was assumed that once the initial cyclic hardening process was complete the fibres were loading and unloading elastically in the composites, thus considerably simplifying the analysis of the results.

In order to put the tensile and cyclic properties of the composites into perspective Figure 3 shows the tensile and cyclic stress-strain curves for unreinforced copper, a composite containing 0.526 V_f of 40 μm diameter fibres and the behaviour of the matrix in the same material after the contribution due to the fibres has been subtracted using the rule of mixtures equation. In this particular case the matrix tensile curve shows a dip around 0.3% strain, which was observed previously⁽⁸⁾ in the tensile behaviour of composites containing 40 and 50 μm diameter.

3.3 Friction stress

For most conventional materials closed hysteresis loops are observed on first plotting load-unload cycles; the value of the friction stress can easily be calculated. A plot of the irreversible work, W , (i.e. the hysteresis loop area) against the dislocation strains, $\Delta\epsilon_d$, (the amount of deviation from elastic behaviour at the maximum stress of the loop) has a shape as shown in Figure 4. The slope of this curve at zero plastic strain has been shown to be equal to twice the composite friction stress, σ_{cf} , i.e.

$$\Delta W = 2\sigma_{cf} \Delta\epsilon_d \quad \dots (3)$$

Figure 4 shows an example of the calculation of σ_{cf} for a composite containing 0.447 V_f of 42.4 μm diameter tungsten wire. Half the slope at zero dislocation strain gives a value of σ_{cf} of 52 MN/m². The composite friction stress for each composite tested is listed in Table I and are plotted against V_f in Figure 5. It can be seen that σ_{cf} increases in a linear fashion with V_f ; extrapolation to $V_f = 0$ gives a friction stress close to the measured value for the unreinforced polycrystalline copper specimen. Included in Figure 5 are the values of Hughes and Rutherford⁽¹²⁾ for the friction stress of copper-tungsten composites prepared by melt infiltration techniques which produced a matrix which is essentially single crystal. The latter fact may account for the plotted results being below those of the present experiments. A broken line in Figure 5 represents the level of the calculated 'rule of mixture' values for the friction stress obtained by drawing a straight line between the observed friction

stress for copper and the elastic stress in tungsten which would exist at the corresponding strain. This is an approximation because of variations in this strain value, however the deviation of the experimental composite friction stress values from this line is so marked that such small errors may be neglected.

If the fibres in the composites undergoing cyclic strain are considered to be elastic this friction stress must arise from the behaviour of the matrix. Such values may be converted to matrix friction stresses, σ_{mf} , by applying the appropriate form of the 'rule of mixtures' equation:

$$\sigma_{mf} = \frac{\sigma_{cf} - \sigma_f V_f}{(1 - V_f)} \quad \dots (4)$$

where σ_f is the elastic stress in the fibre at the strain corresponding to the friction stress. σ_f can be expressed by the relationship:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{\sigma_{cf}}{E_c} \cdot E_f \quad \dots (5)$$

where E_f and E_c are the experimental values of the fibre and composite modulus (given in a previous paper⁽⁸⁾). By combining equations (4) and (5) the matrix friction stress for all composites may be calculated from:

$$\sigma_{mf} = \frac{\sigma_{cf}}{(1 - V_f)} \left[1 - \frac{E_f V_f}{E_c} \right] \quad \dots (6)$$

The resultant values are given in Table I. In comparison with the σ_{cf} values it is to be noted that the range of σ_{mf} values at each wire diameter is reduced. A discussion of the effects of wire diameter and volume fraction on matrix friction stress is given in section 4.2.

3.4 Matrix 0.1% and 0.4% proof stresses

By assuming the tungsten fibres to be elastic during cycling and by subtracting the effect due to the fibres from the composite cyclic stress-strain curves, using the appropriate form of the rule of mixtures equation, the cyclic stress-strain curves for the matrix were derived. From these curves the values of the cyclic matrix 0.1% and 0.4% proof stress values were obtained. These are listed in Table I and are plotted against fibre volume fraction in Figure 6. It can be seen that the proof stress values rise initially and tend to level out at volume fractions in excess of 0.2. The results show that the matrix in

the composite is capable of being cyclically hardened to an extent which is much greater than that of copper in the absence of fibres.

3.5 Matrix cyclic strain hardening exponent

The cyclic stress-strain behaviour of materials can, in general, be expressed in the form:

$$\Delta\sigma = \sigma_0 + k(\Delta\epsilon_d)^n \quad \dots (7)$$

where $\Delta\sigma$ is the cyclic stress amplitude, σ_0 is the elastic limit under cyclic conditions, $\Delta\epsilon_d$ is the dislocation strain amplitude and k and n are constants. A plot of $\log(\sigma - \sigma_0)$ against $\log(\Delta\epsilon_d)$ produces a straight line having a slope equal to 'n' and on extrapolation to $\epsilon_d = 1$ the value of 'k'. The values of 'k' and 'n' obtained for the composites are listed in Table I. It can be seen that for the majority of the materials the 'n' and 'k' values are approximately constant, bearing in mind the likely errors in the determination. The 'k' value can be considered to represent the level of matrix hardening which is achieved and the 'n' value the rate at which this occurs. This means that for materials with approximately the same 'n' values any differences in the 'k' values reflect an inherently greater hardness. This is apparent when considering copper and the composite containing 0.082 V_f of 10.6 μm fibres. They both have an 'n' value of 0.32 whereas the 'k' values are 700 MN/m^2 and 1400 MN/m^2 respectively.

3.6 Specific damping capacity

The specific damping capacity (SDC) of a material is defined as the ratio of the energy absorbed per cycle (as given by the loop area) to the energy represented by the area under the stress-strain curve. When the hysteresis loops are narrow the SDC is approximately equal to the ratio of the loop area to half the maximum stress times the strain plus half the loop area. The SDC was calculated for all the composites tested from measurements on the stable hysteresis loops. The results are plotted against dislocation strain (ϵ_d) in Figure 7. It can be seen from the curves that the SDC increases rapidly with strain at low values of ϵ_d , tending to level out at the higher strain values. In addition, the SDC values increase as the fibre volume fraction reduces. This is seen more clearly in Figure 8 which shows a plot of SDC at 10^{-3} strain against fibre volume fraction. The points for all the specimens fall on a single curve, irrespective of fibre diameter suggesting that the SDC is largely connected with the amount of matrix material present rather than any other factor. In order to test this idea the SDC was normalised with respect to matrix by dividing the values by the appropriate matrix volume fraction. This line is also shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that the SDC is not simply dependent on

the amount of matrix present.

4.0 Discussion

The results reported in section 3 indicate that significant deviation from predictable 'rule of mixtures' behaviour when these composites are subjected to cycling through a fairly wide plastic strain range. Cyclic hardening of the matrix was shown to be in excess of that attributed to the dense tangle of dislocations between fibres after fabrication process involving heating, see Figure 3. The cyclic behaviour of the tungsten-copper composites will be analysed in this section to determine whether the distribution of "thermally induced" dislocations significantly alters the pattern of cyclic hardening throughout the plastic strain range examined.

4.1 Behaviour at low cyclic stresses

The load-unload behaviour at low stresses as shown in Figure 1 is not typical of the behaviour of conventional materials under the same conditions. On progressively increasing the cyclic stress in the latter case elastic loading and unloading would occur at first followed by a closed hysteresis corresponding to the reversible movement of dislocations. Then an open loop would be observed where some of the dislocations are unable to return on removing the stress. Such open loops may be persuaded to close by continued cycling at the same stress level.

In the present series of composites the above behaviour was not observed. An explanation for the observed phenomena could involve the thermally induced dislocation distribution in the matrix, which may be considered to be metastable. It may be moved towards equilibrium by the cyclic stress pattern. Hence, dislocations which are moved during the initial application of the tensile stress are unable to move back when the stress is removed because they have achieved a more stable configuration, this will result in an elastic unloading response (see Figure 1 loop 2). A further justification of this approach can be seen when discussing the friction stress in section 4.2.

4.2 Friction stress

As shown in Figure 5 the composite friction stress, σ_{cf} , showed a considerable deviation from that expected from the 'rule of mixtures' calculation. Since the fibres are behaving in an elastic manner at such stress levels it is more probable that such deviations arise from matrix behaviour. From these measurements values of the matrix friction stress, σ_{mf} , were calculated and are given in Table I and plotted in Figure 9. Instead of plotting the data against V_f the values of σ_{mf} have

been related to $(V_f/a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$. Such a procedure allows an account to be taken of fibre diameter, d , i.e. the interfibre spacing, a , (fibre surface to fibre surface) is related for an hexagonal array of fibres through an equation:

$$a = d \left[\left(\frac{\pi}{2(3V_f)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1 \right] \quad \dots (8)$$

The parameter $(V_f/a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ was used in a previous paper⁽⁸⁾ to represent the dislocation density in the 'softest' part of the matrix, i.e. midway between the fibres. Figure 9 shows an approximate linear relationship between matrix friction stress and the above parameter, also the line extrapolates back to the frictional stress for the unreinforced polycrystalline copper. It is to be noted that a matrix friction stress value calculated from the results of Hughes and Rutherford⁽¹²⁾ for essentially single crystal copper (reinforced with 130 μm diameter tungsten wire) is again below those found in the present work.

The results suggest that the friction stress of the matrix is also a function of the overlap of the dislocation distributions as was the case for the microyield stress for the matrix reported earlier⁽⁸⁾. However, care must be exercised when trying to interpret the results in terms of those for non reinforced metals because in the case of the composite closed loops were never observed in the absence of prestrain, see Figure 1. This means that the friction stress in the present experiments represents the stress necessary to initiate dislocation motion in the matrix after an initial rearrangement of the dislocations, i.e. beyond loop 6 in Figure 1.

For conventional materials the friction stress value is commonly found to be half the elastic limit. However, in the present experiments the values for the matrix friction stress as given in Figure 9 are found to be approximately equal to the values of the matrix microyield stress⁽⁸⁾. This is thought to be a consequence of the behaviour of the composites which prevents the formation of closed hysteresis loops without prestrain being present. Hence, the friction stress as measured here is the value for prestrained material, as prestraining was a prerequisite for the formation of a closed hysteresis loop. It is well known that friction stress increases with prestrain in copper without reinforcement⁽¹³⁾.

4.3 Matrix proof stresses and cyclic hardening

It was shown in section 3.4 that the 0.1% and 0.4% proof stress values for the matrix increased with volume fraction up to $\sim 0.2 V_f$, thereafter remaining approximately constant. This implies that the cyclic proof stress is independent of the interfibre spacing in these composites unlike the tensile 0.1%

proof stress which was found to increase with decreasing inter-fibre spacing^(7,8). When copper is subject to cyclic stresses a dislocation substructure builds up to give a cell size of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$. This is considerably less than the lowest inter-fibre spacing value of $12 \mu\text{m}$ in the present experiments, and may explain why the matrix behaviour is independent of inter-fibre spacing at the level of cyclic strain which leads to the build up of a dislocation substructure in the matrix.

It is not clear at this stage why the proof stress values increase with volume fraction at low volume fractions and level out above 0.2. It may be that the resulting dislocation substructure is related to the initial dislocation density in the matrix which in turn is related to V_f , bearing in mind the overlapping of dislocation distributions discussed earlier.

It can be seen from Table I that there is a tendency for the cyclic hardening exponent 'n' and the constant 'k' to be independent of fibre diameter and volume fraction. This confirms the evidence from Figure 6 that the 0.1% and 0.4% proof stress values flatten out above $V_f = 0.2$ and both plots show a similar rate of increase of plastic strain below this volume fraction.

4.4 Specific Damping Capacity

The initial rise of damping capacity with dislocation strain, see Figure 7, indicates that the cyclic deformation of the matrix is a major contribution to this property. The contribution from this source does not continue to rise at the same rate as the cyclic strain level increases. Nevertheless, the strain at which the damping capacity effectively levels out does appear to increase with matrix fraction. Rather surprisingly the damping capacity at 0.1% plastic strain shows a greater deviation at higher fibre volume fractions from the normalised values (normalised with respect to the matrix fraction), see Figure 8. Explanations for these observations could involve either relative movement between the fibres and the matrix or plastic deformation of the fibres. At the strain levels concerned fibre plasticity is possible in monotonic testing, however in the testing of extracted tungsten wires it has been shown that such materials cyclically harden after one cycle and then behave in essentially an elastic manner.

4.5 Fatigue behaviour

The observed cyclic hardening behaviour may be used to interpret the low and high cycle fatigue strengths of fibre reinforced metals. More positive statements may be made about low cycle-large strain amplitude fatigue where difficulties have been experienced^(1,2) in predicting fatigue behaviour from the Manson-Coffin relationship:

$$N_f^{\frac{1}{2}} \Delta \epsilon_p = \text{a constant} \quad \dots (9)$$

where N_f is the number of cycles to failure. In such cases the measured fatigue values were usually in excess of those forecast from the combined application of equations (2) and (9). From Figure 3 and Table I it is apparent throughout the strain range that the level of matrix hardening was much above that expected in unreinforced copper. Hence, the value of U , the effective modulus of the yielded matrix in cyclic loading, referred to in equation (2), will be raised, which in turn will reduce the value of $\Delta \epsilon$. A lower $\Delta \epsilon$ value according to equation (9) will produce a conjugate increase in fatigue life. This finding is in keeping with the observed tension-tension fatigue behaviour⁽¹⁴⁾ of these weakly bonded composites.

At significant levels of cyclic plastic strain ($> 0.1\%$) it is clear that matrix hardening is virtually independent of fibre volume fraction and diameter, i.e. above $\sim 0.2 V_f$, see Figure 6 and Table I. Therefore, in low cycle fatigue it would be expected that the number of cycles to failure would be independent of interfibre spacing. Some confirmation of this reasoning has been given by Harris and Lee⁽¹⁴⁾ who have shown with a series of weakly bonded tungsten-copper composites that variations in wire diameter (20 - 50 μm) at constant V_f (0.37) did not produce any significant change in fatigue life.

At smaller strain amplitudes the influence of interfibre spacing on high cycle fatigue life may be significant. In this case the presence of a 'thermally induced' dislocation pattern (from the fabrication process) may alter the cyclic response of the matrix, see Figure 9. Also it is worth noting that if the fibre volume fraction is below 0.2 the fibre spacing may condition the fatigue response at somewhat higher strain amplitudes.

The comments made above refer in general to weakly bonded systems. Before discussing the general arguments for better fatigue lives with decreasing fibre diameter (at constant V_f) it would be important to assess the effects of good interfacial bonding.

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Table I. Cyclic Properties for Tungsten-Copper Composites

Wire diameter d (μm)	Volume fraction V_f	Interfibre spacing a (μm)	Composite Friction Stress σ_{cf} (MN/m^2)	Matrix Friction Stress σ_{mf} (MN/m^2)	Cyclic strain hardening exponent n	Cyclic strain hardening constant k (MN/m^2)	Cyclic matrix 0.1% proof stress (MN/m^2)	Cyclic matrix 0.4% proof stress (MN/m^2)
10.6	0.082	25	19	16	0.32	1400	190	-
10.6	0.117	19	22	19	0.36	2000	200	300
10.6	0.188	13	32.5	25	0.34	2000	250	390
22.0	0.177	28	27	21	0.34	2200	230	360
22.0	0.247	20	47	34	0.46	4400	245	405
22.0	0.382	12	52	37	-	-	285	-
31.2	0.277	25	40	-	0.31	2000	295	420
31.2	0.337	20	52	33	0.35	2400	260	395
31.2	0.424	14	52	34	0.41	4000	305	510
42.4	0.371	24	45	27	0.40	4300	315	-
42.4	0.447	18	52	31	0.39	2900	250	390
42.4	0.526	13	72	40	0.35	2500	290	415
50.4	0.396	26	34	20	0.32	1900	255	355
50.4	0.472	19	41	23	0.32	1900	255	365
50.4	0.567	13	72	33	0.36	1000	225	290
Copper	-	-	-	6	0.32	700	150	-

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Figure 1. A schematic diagram showing typical loading and unloading behaviour of an as pressed composite.

Figure 2. Cyclic stress-strain curves for copper-tungsten composites. In each case the first number refers to the nominal fibre diameter in μm and the number in brackets is the fibre volume fraction.

Figure 3. Monotonic tensile and cyclic stress-strain curves for a composite containing 0.526 V_f of 40 μm diameter tungsten fibres. Also on the plot are the corresponding stress-strain curves for unreinforced copper and the composite matrix.

Figure 4. A typical plot of hysteresis loop area against dislocation strain from which the friction stress may be calculated.

Figure 5. The relationship between composite friction stress and V_f . (The numbers in the key are nominal fibre diameters in μm).

Figure 6. Variations in proof stress values with changes in fibre volume fraction.

Figure 7. A plot of specific damping capacity against dislocation strain for the range of composites tested.

Figure 8. The variation of specific damping capacity with increasing fibre volume fraction; the normalised line i.e. SDC/V_m should be horizontal if the only contribution to the damping comes from the matrix.

Figure 9. A relationship between matrix friction stress and $(V_f/a^2)^{1/2}$, the latter being related to the dislocation density between the fibres.